

PIISA

Piloting Innovative Insurance
Solutions for Adaptation

D5.3 Project Management Guide – Version 3

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Summary

The Project Management Guide puts together all the necessary guidelines for the effective project management. The objective has been that all the persons working in the PIISA project have had sufficient knowledge of the issues that may affect their work in the project. These have included e.g., means of internal communication, decision making structures and bodies, meeting timetables, producing Deliverables, and monitoring Key Performance Indicators. The Project Management Guide has also aimed to offer guidance where to ask help in problematic situations. All the people working in the project have been encouraged to familiarise themselves with these guidelines. This Version 3 of the Project Management Guide also summarizes the status of the project management at the end of the project.

Keywords

Management, internal communication, Executive Board, meetings, Deliverables, Key performance Indicators, General Assembly, External Advisory Board

Abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Description
CDSEP	Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Plan
CSS	Clay soil shrink-swell
CSSBDA	Clay Shrink Swell Building Damage Assessor
EAB	External Advisory Board
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
GA	General Assembly
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

This is the final updated Version 3 of PIISA Project Management Guide. Version 1 was written in autumn 2023 as a deliverable for the PIISA project. This report summarizes the status of the project management.

2 Project Guides

Besides this Project Management Guide, also other PIISA Guides are updated at the end of the project to present the status of the activities. These include:

- Project Administration Guide – Version 3
- Project Risks and Ethics Guide – Version 3
- Project Data Management Plan – Version 3
- Project communication, dissemination and stakeholder engagement plan CDSEP – Version 3
 - [PIISA_D4.6_CDSEP-Plan-version-3.pdf](#)

3 Management structure and decision-making bodies

For the effective management of PIISA, the following bodies were established at the beginning of the project.

3.1 Management Team

The Management Team coordinated the preparation of all required periodic activity and management reports and project reviews for the EC. The Management Team followed progress on project tasks, deliverables, and budget usage and reported any deviations and corrective actions put in place.

The Management Team coordinated project internal communication related to management and towards the EC. The group maintained relevant internal mailing lists and other channels to guarantee smooth and efficient communication within the consortium.

The Management Team was responsible for organizing meetings, including consortium meetings, regular follow-up meetings and the external Advisory Board meetings.

The original members of the Management Team were:

- Hilppa Gregow, coordinator
- Anna Luomaranta, project manager
- Eeva Kuntsi-Reunanen, risk manager

- Kaisa Juhanko, data manager
- Lauri Uusi-Hakala, administration manager
- Heikki Tuomenvirta, vice coordinator

At a later stage, the members were changed based on work balance and timetable challenges:

- Hilppa Gregow, coordinator
- Anna Luomaranta, project manager
- Kaisa Juhanko, data manager and risks- and ethics manager
- Reetta Lesonen, project administration expert
- Heikki Tuomenvirta, vice coordinator

In addition, Eeva Kuntsi-Reunanen acted as the moderator for the final event and Lauri Uusi-Hakala as a support if especially needed.

The e-mail address for the Management Team: piisamanagement@fmi.fi

3.2 Executive Board (EB)

The Executive Board (EB) consisted of the Management Team and the WP leaders and co-leaders. The Executive Board was responsible for implementation of the project plan and for conducting internal and external evaluations for the deliverables.

The Executive Board had the overall responsibility to ensure that the deliverables of the project were produced on time and to the required quality level.

The members of the Executive Board were:

- Hilppa Gregow, FMI, coordinator, WP5 leader
- Anna Luomaranta, FMI, project manager, WP5 co-leader
- Eeva Kuntsi-Reunanen, FMI, risk manager
- Kaisa Juhanko, FMI, data manager
- Lauri Uusi-Hakala, FMI, administration manager
- Heikki Tuomenvirta, FMI, vice coordinator, WP3 leader
- Jaroslav Mysiak, CMCC, WP1 leader
- Peter Robinson, VU, WP1 co-leader
- Stefano Ceolotto, CMCC, WP1 co-co-leader
- Laura Trentini, Amigo, WP2 leader, WP3 co-leader
- Angel G. Munoz, replaced by Sheetal Saklani from spring 2025 onwards, BSC, WP2 co-leader
- Ariane Kaploun, AXA Climate, WP3 co-co-leader
- Kati Berninger, Tyrsky, WP4 leader
- Adriaan Perrels, Tyrsky, WP4 co-leader

Also, here at the later stage minor changes took place for work and time allocation balance purposes:

- Hilppa Gregow, FMI, coordinator, WP5 leader (active)
- Anna Luomaranta, FMI, project manager, WP5 co-leader (active)
- Kaisa Juhanko, FMI, data and risks and ethics manager (active)
- Reetta Lesonen, FMI project administration expert (support)
- Heikki Tuomenvirta, FMI, vice coordinator, WP3 leader (active)
- Peter Robinson, VU, WP1 co-leader (active)

- Stefano Ceolotto, CMCC, WP1 co-co-leader (active)
- Jaroslav Mysiak, CMCC, WP1 leader (support)
- Laura Trentini, Amigo, WP2 leader, WP3 co-leader (active)
- Sheetal Saklani from spring 2025 onwards, BSC, WP2 co-leader (active)
- Ariane Kaploun, AXA Climate, WP3 co-co-leader (active)
- Kati Berninger, Tyrsky, WP4 leader (active)
- Adriaan Perrels, Tyrsky, WP4 co-leader (support)

The e-mail address for the EB: piisaexecutive@fmi.fi.

3.3 General Assembly (GA)

The General Assembly (GA) decided for the project course and amendments. All partners had a selected member in GA who had voting right. Participation in the GA meetings was allowed for each of the project workers. GA met every 6 months.

During the project, the GA representatives of some partners changed. At the end of the project, GA members who had the voting right were:

- Ariane Kaploun (AXA Climate)
- Melissa Herlitz (CMCC)
- David Cooke (Sustainable Finance Observatory)
- Heikki Tuomenvirta (FMI)
- Sheetal Saklani (BSC)
- Kati Berninger (Tyrsky Consulting)
- Laura Grassi (Politecnico di Milan)
- Lisa Benes (LGI)
- Lisette Klok (Climate Adaptation Services)
- Peter Robinson (Stiching VU)
- Sami Myyrä (LocalTapiola)
- Laura Trentini (Amigo)

The mailing list for the General Assembly Voting members: piisavoting@fmi.fi

3.4 External Advisory Board (EAB)

The EAB (External Advisory Board) was assembled from selected stakeholders from adaptation, insurance and climate risk management, platform, and climate service development. EAB was invited to give feedback prior to the General Assemblies and invited to the General Assemblies (hybrid). EAB members were asked to review the Mid-Term Report. They participated in the review meeting and gave valuable comments on the Report. The feedback that was received from them steered the project to be more active towards the EAB. After that, direct requests were made to EAB to e.g., write blog posts and join in specific internal workshops. EAB members also gave presentations or commentaries at several PIISA events. The EAB members were also invited to participate in the PIISA Final Event and some of them joined the meeting.

PIISA Blog posts written by the EAB members:

- [How adaptation and risk management are being integrated into the Common Agricultural Policy \(CAP\) - A brief insight](#) by Pascal Forrer
- [When Every Minute—and Every Euro—Matters](#) by Roberta Boscolo

PIISA webinars and workshops where EAB members gave expert presentations:

- 10 Dec 2024: Webinar: Insights into Climate Adaptation and Insurance Innovation from PIISA, EAB member Alessandro Bonazzi (Generali)
- 11 Sep 2025: Hybrid Webinar - Adaptive Forest Management and Policy to Tackle Climate Risks, EAB member: Sylvestre Coudert, President and Director General, Forestry France
- 11 Dec 2025: Roundtable – Increasing resilience with urban greening - policies enabling finance and insurance, EAB member *Leigh Wolfrom (OECD)*

The members of the EAB were:

- Alessandro Bonazzi
- Francesco Sciascia
- Pascal Forrer
- Vylon Ooms
- Roberta Boscolo
- Samuel Almond
- Sylvestre Coudert
- Markus Melin
- Leigh Wolfrom
- Mikael Hilden
- Jaakko Nuottokari

4 Meetings

4.1 Management team

WP5 Management team had regular meetings to ensure efficient progress of the project. First the meetings took place every Friday. After the midpoint of the project, the WP5 meetings were organized weekly or monthly on Wednesday depending on the needs and the topical issues. Towards the end of the project and the final seminar in Haarlem, in the Netherlands meetings took place more often to ensure the effective planning of the final event and finalization of the project outcomes.

For enhancing the internal and external communication of the project, WP5 established a monthly meeting with WP4 Communication. Especially the coordination of the Task 4.4 was then paid more attention to. The agenda for these meetings included e.g.

- CDSEP plan
- Monitoring the Events registry table and the Collaboration table and follow-up the important events that should be communicated to the consortium.
- PIISA webinars
- Internal newsletter: PIISA Highlights of the Month
- External Newsletter

4.2 Executive Board

Executive Board meetings first took place every three months. After the midpoint of the project, EB meetings took place every two months to enhance the internal communication and coordination of the work. Also, challenges were more easily detected and their solutions implemented when meetings took place more often. Combined with the bi-monthly EB meetings, an open remote meeting for the whole consortium was established for sharing the latest proceedings of the work. The timing of the General Assemblies caused occasionally some changes to the EB meeting timetables.

These regular meetings were organized mainly remotely.

Dates of the EB meetings: 20 Sep 2023, 7 Dec 2023, 14 Mar 2024, 2 May 2024, 4 Jun 2024, 14 Jun 2024, 19 Sep 2024, 12 Dec 2024, 6 Feb 2025, 10 Apr 2025, 18 Sep 2025, 6 Nov 2025, 28 Jan 2026, 13 May 2026

Short consortium meetings were held: 14 Mar 2024, 12 Dec 2024, 6 Feb 2025, 10 Apr 2025, 18 Sep 2025, 28 Jan 2026

In addition, bilateral and process related planning and decision meetings between coordinator and partner(s) were held when needed.

4.3 General Assembly

The General Assemblies were organized every six months. Most of these were organized remotely to reduce carbon footprints, to save travel costs and to mitigate the risks of travel limitations on project progress. Mid-Term meeting was organized in Paris in Nov 2024 and together with PIISA Final Seminar a consortium meeting was organized in Amsterdam on 5th Mar 2026.

The dates of the General Assemblies and consortium meetings related to them:

- 15-16 Jun 2023: Kick-off meeting and General Assembly on 16 Jun 2023, in-person meeting in Helsinki

- 14 Dec 2023: Consortium meeting and General Assembly, remote meeting
- 20-21 May 2024: Consortium meeting and General Assembly on 21 May 2024, remote meeting
- 14-15 Nov 2024: Consortium meeting and General Assembly on 15 Nov, in-person meeting in Paris
- 4-5 Jun 2025: Consortium meeting and General Assembly on 5 Jun, hybrid meeting in Helsinki and in Teams
- 5 Mar 2026: Consortium meeting, in person in Amsterdam after the Final event held on 4th March
- 22 May 2026: Consortium meeting and General Assembly, remote meeting

5 Internal communication

After the midpoint of the project, it was decided that WP4 and WP5 will be together responsible for coordinating internal communication. WP5 was responsible for internal communication related to decision-making, administration and general management of the project. WP4 planned and used tools and methods for internal communication as well as organized internal workshops if needed. This part of the internal communication is described in The Project communication, dissemination and stakeholder engagement plan CDSEP – Versions 1, 2 and 3. WP4 also created templates for Deliverables and PowerPoint presentations.

To ensure effective internal communication within the project, several mailing lists were created.

- piisamanagement@fmi.fi: Management Team members
- piisawpleads@fmi.fi: WP leaders and co-leaders
- piisaexecutive@fmi.fi: Executive Board members
- piisa@fmi.fi: all the people working in PIISA
- Mailing lists for the work packages:
 - o Piisawp1@fmi.fi
 - o Piisawp2@fmi.fi
 - o Piisawp3@fmi.fi
 - o Piisawp4@fmi.fi

The updates to the recipients of the lists were made weekly based on the requests.

At the beginning of the project, WP5 sent Management Info Letters to the consortium to update partners about topical management issues. After the midpoint of the project, WP5 and WP4 decided to establish a new monthly internal newsletter. It replaced the monthly Management Info Letters sent by WP5 and the quarterly newsletters sent by WP4. The name of this new letter was “PIISA Highlights of the Month” and it was coordinated and sent by WP4 and WP5 together. The letter included information about the finished Deliverables and the Deliverables under preparation as well as the Milestones. Also, topical highlights of PIISA work in different WPs were included.

For sharing the documents, FMI Microsoft Teams Space was used. The Management Team members were the owners of the space and could grant access to it.

In the Teams space (Fig. 1) there were separate folders for each work package: WP1 Insurance, WP2 Climate Service, WP3 Pilots, WP4 Communication, and WP5 Management. Besides these, in the General folder there were subfolders for the Agreements, Submitted deliverables, Recordings and Literature. Also living documents for all to fill in were placed in the General folder.

Other important documents, such as the list of deliverables, milestones, workplan and the Gantt chart could also be found in the General folder.

Figure 1. Structure of PIISA Teams space

6 Deliverables

The Management team had the main responsibility to ensure that the deliverables of the project were produced on time and to the required quality level. All the WP and Task leaders had the responsibility of leading the work in their WPs and organizing the review process for their deliverables. The first production of deliverables was managed at the WP level.

The practicalities concerning the commenting of deliverables included:

- At least 1-3 experts (not authors) within PIISA commented on the deliverable.

- The responsible WP leader or the person responsible for the deliverable decided the reviewers from other Tasks depending on the relevance of the deliverable and the expertise of persons.
- Deliverables were to be sent to selected reviewers for comments one month before the final deadline, unless another review period had been agreed upon with the reviewers.

The project manager Anna Luomaranta submitted the deliverables to the EC. Before the final submission, the quality of all deliverables was checked at 3 levels by:

(i) the partner responsible for producing the deliverable;

(ii) the WP leader; and

(iii) the coordinator.

7 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

PIISA had several Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that were monitored throughout the project. Work Packages were responsible for achieving the KPIs indicated to them in Table 1. The KPI progress at the middle of the project has been reported in the project status report: D5.2 Project Management Guide – Version 2 (M18). The final status of KPIs is seen in Table 1.

Some of the KPIs needed to be interpreted differently due to external factors. These included, e.g. the change of Twitter to X. However, X turned out not to be a reliable platform for project communication and dissemination. Thus, GA decided to move the project communication to LinkedIn, which affected KPI 17.

The rate of development in EU regulation and carbon credit markets was slower than expected. Particularly, forest and soil carbon credits are currently not yet part of the compliance carbon market in the EU. This external limitation affected carbon credit insurance development relevant for KPIs 13 and 15. The solution was to reallocate the resources within relevant tasks for development of more advanced forest wind damage and wildfire insurances than originally planned.

As for the events, PIISA co-organized several events with other projects. PIISA also organized more own events than was originally planned. This affected the interpreting and reporting of KPI 21 and 24.

Table 1. The PIISA key performance indicators.

Adaptation and insurance gap filling KPIs	Target	Status (May 2026)
KPI 1 (D1.3, D2.2, D3.1, D3.5, D4.2) Climate risks regarding city and well-being, food, and agriculture as well as forest	PIISA mapping and surveying responses will be high, and	Surveys have been conducted in WP1, collecting 951 responses from 6 European countries (Finland, France, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Spain), focusing on climate change awareness, previous

<p>growth risks will be better presented and awareness in the need to adapt will be rising. (WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4)</p>	<p>awareness can be seen from them.</p>	<p>damages from climate-related events, insurance coverage and knowledge about NBS.</p> <p>An in-person workshop with the olive farmers in Jaen was organized to collect rich data on climate risk awareness, historical losses, insurance gaps and demand.</p> <p>Web site explaining what is CSS event damage risk as well as economic risk to home owners in France launched.</p> <p>A broader scope farmer survey was disseminated using the digital network of ASAJA Jaen and responses were collected from 47 farmers in the Andalucia region of Spain. The survey included sections on climate risk awareness, past losses, climate risk management, insurance gaps and co-design.</p> <p>3 workshops conducted for D1.3 to increase awareness to risks across pilots</p>
<p>KPI 2 (D1.2, D1.4) Knowledge on adaptation alternatives employing Nature-Based-Solutions (NBS) will be rising. (WP1)</p>	<p>Collection of NBS published and liked (> 1000) in Twitter (as Twitters role changed due to the geopolitical situation, we in PIISA decided to be involved in essential social media accounts – such as LinkedIn and calculate the overall record).</p>	<p>NBS infocard, CAS report and blog posts on NBS published and liked on LinkedIn & X: impressions 4700 / reactions 72</p>
<p>KPI 3 (D4.7) Business models for NBS and insurance will be developed, demonstrated and the replication strategy documented. (WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4)</p>	<p>Published in open access journals.</p>	<p>The Foresight publication at CMCC accepted the short article on D4.7 in May 2026: https://www.climateforesight.eu/articles/business-models-for-urban-nature-based-solutions-and-insurance/</p>
<p>KPI 4 (D3.2) PIISA granular climate adaptation dashboard will complement EIOPA’s bottom-up approach by providing very local data and translating the scientific and meteorological data regarding the protection gaps for natural catastrophes (hazards are earthquakes,</p>	<p>Vulnerability, exposure, and insurance coverage will be built in the PIISA Adaptation dashboard for Citizens.</p>	<p>We didn’t develop a separate PIISA dashboard but all the tools for supporting adaptation in insurance and finance sector have been implemented to the PIISA website which operates more broadly. The following tools can be accessed:</p> <p>Clay-Shrink-Swell Building Damage Assessor (CSSBDA)</p>

<p>floods, wildfires, and windstorms) into financial terms. (WP1, WP2, WP3)</p>		<p>Awareness Tool on Innovative Insurance Solutions: Green Roofs</p> <p>CoDepi (Co-Designing Parametric Insurance) participatory tool to support the design of index-based climate insurance solution for agriculture.</p> <p>Shiny App for Seasonal Forecasts.</p> <p>The ten novel climate risk indicators (see KPI 6) with links to the DRMCK's Risk Data Hub and the Impact data catalogue are described on the website.</p>
<p>KPI 5 (D2.2, D3.6) PIISA granular climate adaptation dashboard will be co-designed rapidly because in the co-development phase, the PIISA consortium will employ several state-of-the-art tools which we learned to exist during the proposal preparation phase. (WP2, WP3)</p>	<p>Entering as planned to pilot the PIISA Adaptation Dashboard for citizens to support efforts of EIOPA.</p>	<p>Data sources and tools relevant to the project were mapped and integrated into the development loops (engagement with citizens and stakeholders) to support reaching KPI 4.</p>
<p>Piloting process KPIs</p>	<p>Target</p>	
<p>KPI 6 (WP2, WP3 and WP5) Nr of novel piloted open-source risk indicators integrated to Risk Data Hub</p>	<p>> 10</p>	<p>Risk Data Hub has received all the datasets produced within PIISA. The final number was 10 risk indicators. They are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Climate Dryness Index (CDI) - Three-Month Dry Accumulation Probability Index (DAP150) - Yield loss drought index - Standardized Precipitation and Growth Index (SPGI) - Hail index - Thunder day index - Severe thunder day index - Wind Power Exposure Index (WPEI) - Standardized Windstorm Index (SWI) - Catalogue of Stochastic Wildfire Simulations
<p>KPI 7 (WP3 D3.14) Nr of pilot domains (sector-product combinations)</p>	<p>10</p>	<p>14 pilot domains (See Table 2)</p>

KPI 8 (WP3, WP5 D3.2) Nr of areas piloted (EEA climate risk zones, countries, regions, cities)	> 10	17 pilot-country combinations (see Table 3)
KPI 9 (WP5 D5.11, D5.12) Growth rate of clients interested in parametric insurance solutions	Based on surveys: increasing	The concept of parametric insurance was introduced in several workshops, surveys and webinars (on-site or online) including participants who didn't know about it. After the events, participants who were not familiar with parametric insurance before the event became interested in them. See deliverables D3.7, D3.8, D3.11 and D3.13.
KPI 10 (WP2, WP3, D3.2) Nr of domain pilot demonstrations based on Destination Earth simulations	1	One simulation demonstration was performed. Data from three historical ignition locations identified in the Portugal region were used as WISE fire spread modelling input. These locations were in close proximity to the planned fuel breaks in forested areas. Fire spread was simulated using current vegetation and with fuel breaks implemented. Results show clear reduction in fire spread in the areas; the fuel breaks having a major impact on the overall area burned.
KPI 11 (WP1 and WP2, D2.3) Open sharing solutions for hazard risks, damage risks and insurance will be in use by supervisors for adaptation and insurance companies when pilots are tested and considered functional. The PIISA granular platform will be open-access.	TRL from 5 to 7-8	TRL 5-7. See KPI 6. Also tools CSSBDA, CoDepi and Awareness Tool on Innovative Insurance Solutions (Green Roofs) were implemented on the PIISA Web site.
KPI 12 (WP2, WP3 and WP5, D5.12) Seasonal forecasts will be semi-operational and disseminated via C3S as outlooks and tailored for agriculture for the farmers and insurers during the growing season.	TRL from 5 to 7-8	TRL 7. Demonstration of Shiny app tool on Seasonal Forecasts for the Olive Oil Sector in the Iberian Peninsula produced by CSC based on C3S products.
KPI 13 (WP1, WP3 and WP4) For the local forests, novel microclimatic quick simulations will be applicable for carbon insurance solution testing and	TRL from 5 to 7	The carbon insurance solution was translated into a wildfire insurance concept, as fire is a major driver of carbon release and destruction of carbon sink. The wildfire concept advanced to TRL 6 (the level and link with carbon is explained in D.3.13). A product directly insuring a carbon level turned out

<p>support immediate adaptation gap filling.</p>		<p>to be too complicated for the resources that were available and due to the slow development of EU regulation and carbon credit markets.</p> <p>The wildfire insurance concept will also provide broader applications than only carbon considerations. The economic impacts related to wildfires and the need for carbon insurance has been discussed and brainstormed with GHG mitigation experts (D3.13).</p>
<p>KPI 14 (WP2) For the forests in the EU, novel indicators for mid- and long-term adaptation planning will be developed and can be further developed.</p>	<p>TRL from 3 to 4</p>	<p>TRL 6. Novel vulnerability indicators of the forest wind damages have been defined and used in the beta product of Forest wind damage insurance. Detailed descriptions can be found in D3.13. Management actions affecting these indicators can be used as basis for mid- and long-term adaptation planning in forestry. Besides these, the Wind Power Exposure Index (WPEI) was developed and implemented to Risk Data Hub.</p>
<p>KPI 15 (WP1 and WP3) Carbon farming insurance will be demonstrated.</p>	<p>TRL from 3 to 4</p>	<p>TRL 3. Agriculture pilot focused on the co-development of a concept of index-based insurance adaptable to different crops and perennials (see D3.12). A severe limitation for insurance demonstration was that forests and soil carbon credits are currently not yet part of the compliance carbon market in the EU. (see KPI 13) For the carbon farming insurance further development is needed.</p>
<p>Engagement, Dissemination, and Communication items and measures in WP4 and monitoring in WP5</p>	<p>Target</p>	
<p>KPI 16 (D4.2, D4.6) Project website</p>	<p>> 12000 visitors</p>	<p>34489 visits (May 21 2026)</p>
<p>KPI 17 (D4.2, D4.6) social media</p>	<p>> 1000 total followers</p>	<p>1009 followers</p>
<p>KPI 18 (D4.2, D4.6) Newsletters</p>	<p>> 200 subscribers</p>	<p>167 subscribers</p>
<p>KPI 19 (D4.6, D5.3) PIISA presented in conferences and events</p>	<p>> 40 events attended</p>	<p>45 events attended</p>

KPI 20 (D5.9) Scientific publications	> 10 publications submitted	10-13. See Table 4.
KPI 21 (D4.6, D4.8, D4.9, D5.3) Webinar series (3 webinars)	> 1000 total attendees	PIISA organized many events and webinars. In many of those, participation was possible both online and on-site. Altogether PIISA events and webinars gathered 1256 attendees. See Table 5 for more information.
KPI 22 (D4.2) Blog	12 posts	13 posts
KPI 23 (D4.4, D4.5, D4.9, D5.3) Policy briefs and white papers	> 2 documents	2 documents
KPI 24 (D4.6, D4.9, D4.10, D5.3) Workshops, round tables and discussion sessions organized	> 10 PIISA events	27 events
KPI 25 (D5.3) Clustering activities with related projects and initiatives	8 projects engaged	The most important ones: P2R, NATURANCE, ClimateFit, ANTICIPATE, DESTINE Climate and DESTINE Extremes, PRECILIENCE, SOTERIA, SWIFTT, TAPSI (Finland). Additionally, several others.
KPI 26 (D4.8, D5.3) Mid-term online event	> 150 attendees	119 attendees
KPI 27 (D4.9, D5.3) Final event	> 150 attendees	104 attendees

Table 2. KPI 7: pilot domains (Product/Tool/Concept combinations)

Product/Tool/Concept	sector 1	sector 2	sector 3	sector 4
CCSDBDA	housing	construction	insurance	
CoDepi	insurance	agriculture		
Awareness Tool on Innovative Insurance Solutions: Green Roofs	insurance	housing	construction	
Parametric forest wind damage insurance beta product	insurance	forestry		
Novel wildfire insurance concept	insurance	forestry	housing	disaster risk management

Table 3. KPI 8: Areas piloted (countries)

Pilot	Country 1	Country 2	Country 3	Country 4	Country 5	Country 6
Green roofs	Nether-lands	Finland	Italy			
CSS	France	Finland	Luxem- bourg	Spain	Germany	Italy
Agricult. insurance	Spain	Finland	Italy			
Wind damage insurance	Germany	France	Ireland	Denmark		
Wildfire insurance	Portugal					

Table 4. KPI 20: Scientific publications generated in PIISA.

Authors & affiliations	Title	Journal	Status	DOI link	Linked to WP
Ingels, M.W., Botzen, W.J., Aarts, J.C.J.H., Brusselaars, J., Tesselaar, M. (IVM-VU)	The state of the art and future of climate risk insurance modeling	<i>Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences</i> , Vol.1541, Issue 1, 2024	Published	https://nyaspubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/nyas.15255	WP1
Robinson, P.J., Botzen, W.J. (IVM-VU)	Behavioural public policy for natural disaster preparedness and the role of economic experiments	<i>Humanities and Social Sciences Communications</i> , Article: 719, 2025	Published	https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-025-05086-2	WP1 / WP3
Utriainen L., Virman M., Laakso A., Ritvanen J., Jylhä K. & Merikanto J. (FMI)	Less frequent but more intense summertime precipitation in Finland: results from a convection-permitting climate model.	<i>Boreal Environmental Research</i> , Vol. 30, pp. 93–109. 2025	Published	https://www.borenv.net/BER/archiv e/pdfs/ber30/ber30-093-109.pdf	WP2
Ooms, V., Endendijk, T., Aerts, J.H.J.C., Botzen, W.J. Robinson, P.J. (IVM-VU)	Assessing effects of nature-based and other municipal adaptation measures on insured heavy rain damages	<i>Natural Hazards and Earth Systems Science</i> , Vol.25, pp.4283–4298, 2025	Published	https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-25-4283-2025	WP3
Aragão, L., Borrelli, A., Gualdi, S. (CMCC)	Expanding CMCC seasonal prediction system v3.5 applications to the local scale through statistical downscaling techniques	<i>Atmospheric Research</i> , Vol.336, Article: 108811, 2026	Published	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosres.2026.108811	WP2
Farina, G., Robinson, P.J., Botzen, W.J., van Beukering, P. (IVM-VU)	Pro-social versus pro-self motivations for green roof adoption: Evidence from a discrete choice experiment	<i>Ecological Economics</i> , 1st submission 2025/6; revision submitted 2026/2	Under review		WP3
Tuomenvirta, H., Ruosteenoja, K. (FMI)	Projections of deep and near-surface layer soil moisture for Europe: long-term mean changes and occurrence of severe droughts	<i>International Journal of Climatology</i> Submission 2026/3	Under review		WP2
Ceolotto, S., Colucci, M., Taddeo, S., Mysiak, J. (CMCC)	Unpacking the Barriers to Natural and Climate Risk Insurance Adoption: A Literature Review	<i>International journal of disaster risk reduction</i> Submission 2026/3 (earlier version rejected elsewhere)	Under review		WP1
Carrai, L., Grassi, L. (PoLiMi)	Drivers of Climate Insurance Uptake. A Multi-Hazard Analysis across European Countries	(<i>Ecological Economics</i>), submission 2026/2, rejected 2026/5; revision to be resubmitted to other journal	To be resubmitted to other journal	Submission foreseen before 1.10.2026	WP1

Perrels, A., Huttunen, M. (Tyrsky)	Data collaboration concepts for climate change aware insurance and their implications for the supply and scope of climate aware insurance products	Various journals under consideration	Under preparation	Submission foreseen in June 2026	WP1 / WP3
Galicia, L. (AXA Clima), Koltsele, J. (FMI), Xavier, R. (AGIF), et al	Assessing the effect of fuel break networks to reduce expected economic losses from wildfires	Various journals under consideration	Under preparation	Submission foreseen before 1.10.2026	WP3
Virman, M., Laurila, T., Mäkelä, A. (FMI), Lind, P. (SMHI)	Future projections of convective storm environments in Fennoscandia based on a regional climate model	Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences	Under preparation	Submission foreseen in June 2026	WP2
Saklani, S., Milders, N., Muñoz, A.G. (BSC)	Co-development of an index-based insurance solution for olive farmers in south of Spain	Climate Services	Under preparation	Submission foreseen before 1.10.2026	WP3
Colucci, M., Ceolotto, S., Taddeo, S., Mysiak, J. (CMCC)	European designs for climate-risk insurance systems	<i>Journal of Environmental Economics and Policy</i> , submission 2026/4; rejected 2026/5	No resubmission foreseen prior to final project review		WP1

Table 5. KPI 21. Participant numbers in the most important PIISA events and webinars.

PIISA Events and Webinars (The table does not include the WP1 webinars.)	Participants		
	Online	Onsite	Total
WP1 Workshop 2024 Session 1	104		104
WP1 Workshop 2024 Session 2	64		64
Naturethon – Nature and insurance (co-hosted with Naturance)	66		66
Mid-term webinar 2024	129		129
Webinar 1 Adapting to climate risks through green roofs webinar: Insights from the Netherlands	66		66
Webinar 2 Farmers first: Insurance that works for farmers	73		73
Event: Round table discussion session on adaptation and justice in the NOCCA conference		~ 80	80
Webinar 3 Modelling as a tool to understand wildfire risk and risk reduction potential (co-hosted with ClimateDT)	78		78
WP1 Workshop 2025/round table discussion (co-hosted with SWIFTT)	66	28	94
Event: Round table discussion increasing resilience with urban greening (co-hosted with CLIMATEFIT)	44		44
Event: PIISA Final Seminar	51	51	102
Webinar 4 Climate resilient natural resource management (co-hosted with PRECILIENCE)	75		75
WP1 workshop: From pilots to practice	91		91
Webinar 5 Market feasibility of index-based climate insurance for Mediterranean agriculture	11		11
Webinar 6 Clay shrink-swell property damage ang the emerging insurance protection gap	25		25
Event: Collective insights. Lasting impact session in the NATURANCE festival (co-organized with NATURANCE, SOTERIA, Invest4Nature, and CLIMATEFIT)	71	83	154
Total	1014	242	1256

8 Final reporting

Officially project period ends at the end of May 2026. After that, final reporting will begin. FMI will lead and instruct partners for financial reporting and summarizing overall project results and outcomes. FMI will outline activities for dissemination and exploitation of PIISA project results. Emphasis will be in outcomes for further research and development activities; developing, creating or marketing a product; creating and providing a service; or using them in research-policy knowledge brokering.

